

DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH AND HUMAN SERVICES
PUBLIC HEALTH SERVICE

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
Office of Health and Safety, MS A-46
Atlanta, Georgia 30333
TEL: 404-718-2077, FAX: 404-718-2093; Email: importpermit@cdc.gov

Permit to Import Infectious Biological Agents, Infectious Substances, and Vectors

In accordance with 42 CFR Section 71.54 of the Public Health Service Foreign Quarantine Regulations, cited on the bottom of this permit, permission is granted the permittee to import into any port under control of the United States, or to receive by transfer within the United States, the material described in Item 1 below.

PHS PERMIT NO.	2016-05-167	
DATES	ISSUED: Thursday, May 26, 2016	EXPIRES: Saturday, November 26, 2016
1. DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL	FIELD COLLECTED WATER BACTERIA SPECIMENS IN AGAR WHICH MAY CONTAIN ESCHERICIA COLI.	
2. PERMITTEE (NAME, ORGANIZATION, ADDRESS AND CONTACT INFORMATION)	SWATI RAYASAM UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA AT BERKELEY 50 UNIVERSITY HALL #7360 BERKELEY, CA 94720 TEL: 919-308-8284 FAX:	
3. SOURCE OF MATERIAL (NAME, ORGANIZATION, ADDRESS, COUNTRY)	SWATI RAYASAM INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY BOMBAY CENTRE FOR TECHNOLOGY ALTERNATIVES FOR RURAL AREAS (CTARA) MUMBAI INDIA 400076	
4. TYPE OF PERMIT AND INSTRUCTIONS FOR USE	As the permittee, your facility will be subject to inspection at some time in the future to confirm that the importer's biosafety measures are commensurate with the hazard posed by the items to be imported and the level of risk given its intended use. ☒ Single Importation into the U.S. ☐ Single Transfer Within the U.S. ☐ Multiple Importation into the U.S. ☒ Multiple Transfer Within the U.S. A. Record of each importation shall be maintained on permanent file by permittee. B. Enclosed label(s) must be forwarded to the shipper(s). C. One label shall be affixed to shipping container. Enclosed labels may be photocopied.	
5. CONDITIONS OF ISSUANCE ITEMS APPLICABLE WHEN CHECKED	☐ A. Subsequent distribution, within the U.S., of the material described in this permit is prohibited without prior authorization by the Public Health Service. ☒ B. All material is for laboratory use only - Not for use in the production of biologics for humans or animals. ☒ C. All material is free of tissues, serum and plasma of domestic and wild ruminants, swine and equines. ☐ D. Additional Requirements: ☐ IATA Packaged to preclude escape. ☐ USDA permit may be required (Telephone: 301-851-3300). ☒ E. Work with the agent(s) described shall be restricted to areas and conditions meeting requirements in the CDC/NIH publication "Biosafety in Microbiological and Biomedical Laboratories." ☒ F. Packaging must conform to 49 CFR Sections 171-180.	
	6. Signature of Issuing officer Daniel Sosin, MD, MPH, FACP Acting Director, Division of Select Agents and Toxins	

CDC 0728 (F 13.40) REV. 4-13

42 CFR 71.54. Permit to Import Biological Agents, Infectious Substances, and Vectors
A person may not import into the United States any infectious biological agent, infectious substance, or vector unless: It is accompanied by a permit issued by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). The possession of a permit issued by the CDC does not satisfy permitting requirements placed on materials by the U.S. Department of Agriculture that may pose hazards to agriculture or agricultural production in addition to hazards to human health.

DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH AND HUMAN SERVICES

Public Health Service
Centers for Disease Control
and Prevention (CDC)
Atlanta GA 30333

To: Importer, Public Health Service Import Permit

Subject: Approval to import infectious biological agents, infectious substances or vectors

Attached please find your Public Health Service (PHS) import permit. The PHS import permit is valid only for the material(s), locations and conditions described in your application. Please note that the issuance and expiration dates located on the import permit pertain only to the dates that the importer is allowed to import into the United States the infectious biological agents, infectious substances, and vectors listed on the import permit. These dates do not relate to the conditions of continued possession associated with the permit. The conditions of continued possession listed on the permit remain in affect until the importer is no longer in possession of the imported material. The possession of a permit issued by the CDC does not satisfy permitting requirements placed on materials by the U.S. Department of Agriculture that may pose hazards to agriculture or agricultural production in addition to hazards to human health.

Please be reminded that the permittee must ensure that:

1. The enclosed import permit and labels are forwarded to the shipper(s). The enclosed permit and labels may be photocopied if more are needed.
2. The shipper includes the PHS import permit with the shipping documents and the enclosed label (or copy of label) should be affixed to the outer shipping container.
3. A record of each importation (including permits and shipping documents) is maintained.
4. The shipment of infectious biological agents, infectious substance or vectors must be packaged, labeled, and shipped in accordance with all applicable federal and international regulations. Please note that the issuance of an import permit is not an authorization to hand carry the material.

Please also note that other permits may be required for the importation of infectious biological agents, infectious substances or vectors. If you have questions regarding this correspondence, please contact CDC Import Permit Program at (404)718-2077 or visit our website at <http://www.cdc.gov/od/eaipp/>.

Von McClee, Chief, Program Services Branch
Division of Select Agents and Toxins
Department of Health and Human Services
Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

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10-8-2016

C-Badge

~~Items~~

I, Swati Rayaram, flying on United Flight 849
to Newark, New Jersey, am carrying with me environmental
samples suspended in sterile agar.

Kindly allow me to export this from Mumbai, India.
The purpose of these items is purely academic in nature, and
not for commercial use.

Kindly refer to my information below:

Swati Durga Gayatri Rayaram
498039297

Regards,

US Student GHE
University of California at Berkeley

allama

10/8/16
Hole